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"They had it coming" - Extent and contextual determinants of scientific misconduct in Austria, Germany, and Switzerland¹

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Background and purpose of the study

Since the beginning of times science has been on the quest of describing and explaining, more so understanding the world in an objective as well as unbiased way (Purtill, 1970). Idealistically speaking, scientific research involves behaviour that focuses on values such as honesty, fairness, reliability, scepticism, accountability, and openness (Council, 2012) and is not corrupted by self-interested motivations ('desinterestedness' Merton, 1973, p.275f). Engaging in scientific misconduct goes directly against these notions. As a member of the scientific community, one is subject to the same general expectations as research practices that are not carried out in a scientifically sound way do not serve the overall goal of knowledge accumulation. Naturally, there is no debate as to whether misconduct is ethical or desirable. The scientific community condemns such practices (e.g. Martinson et al., 2005). Nevertheless, misconduct happens (e.g. Martinson et al., 2005).

It is most fascinating to investigate scientific misconduct and yet there is only so much there is known. Current research is focusing mostly on trying to capture its magnitude. While it is important to have a sense of how widespread the problem is, this perspective alone would not contribute to overcoming the problem. Ultimately, the spotlight should light on the area around the iceberg: what is the context in which misconduct happens? Little is known about what systemic reasons exist that trigger scientific misconduct. This allows us not to focus on individuals and their dramatic turns in lives which led to isolated cases of misconduct but instead pay attention to the nurturing setting which allows for this to happen. We argue that focussing on how delinquents trivialize and excuse their misbehavior, i.e. the way they neutralize it, will give fruitful insights on the setting.

Neutralisation is a known phenomenon in the context of criminal offence. The techniques of neutralization describe beliefs that redefine criminal or deviant behavior as justifiable (Sykes & Matza, 1957, p.666). This means that learning these neutralizations allows delinquents to perceive their behavior still as permissible extensions of the law – and not as a breach of the law. Research has found five neutralisation narratives (Sykes & Matza, 1957): (1) denying the responsibility of one own's behaviour, (2) denying the injury resulting from the behaviour, (3)

¹ This project is part of the SNSF Starting Grant BSS-GIO 155981 of Heiko Rauhut ("Social norms, cooperation and conflict in scientific collaborations").

denying the victim who was affected by the behaviour, (4) shifting the blame, and condemning the condemners and (5) appealing to higher loyalties.

The present study: Putting the crime into science

For the first time, we apply them in the context of such violations against the scientific code and ask whether those who neutralize are more likely to commit scientific misconduct. To close the research gap we analyse new, large-scale data based in a web survey conducted in 2020. The study consists of representative data from academic scientists in Austria, Germany, and Switzerland. Following criminological research, we introduced survey items that describe a set of neutralisation techniques (Sykes & Matza, 1957). More specifically, we adapted the techniques to the scientific context and asked the scientists to report whether the statements are relatable.

Deviance in science can manifest itself in various forms and shapes, and institutions provide countless definitions of what constitutes scientific misconduct. For our argument, we expand Steneck (2006) framework of scientific conduct and decided to include the following types of severe scientific misconduct (SSM) in the survey (Rauhut et al., 2020): intentionally manipulating empirical data, publishing parts from third parties without indication, concealing a conflict of interest and making up data. We further decided to include the concealing a clash of interest to the more severe cases as it can be considered as a non compliance with research regulations (Weed, 1998). We asked about the following questionable research practices (QRP) in the survey (Rauhut et al., 2020): being a co-author without having made a substantial contribution, quoting someone in order to gain an advantage from it, reviewing someone positively as a favour, submitting the same results to more journals without indicating it.

In our analyses, we apply a Poisson regression to estimate the correlation between identifying with specific neutralisation techniques and the use of questionable research practices and serious scientific misconduct.

Findings, discussion and conclusions

Table 1 captures the effect of neutralisation techniques on all misconduct items (Model 1), on questionable research practices (Model 2) and on severe scientific misconduct (Model 3). To ensure the interpretability of the results, we converted the estimates to incidence rate ratios (the raw coefficient can be requested). As only a few scientists admitted to the severe malpractices (N= 243) by their self-reports, the following interpretation focuses on questionable research practices (Model 2).

Consistent with expectations, the results of the Model 2 indicate that scientists who score higher on four of the five measures of neutralisation have a higher prevalence to questionable research practices: Each standard deviation increase in the denial of responsibility (IRR = 1.099, $p < 0.000$) and denial of the victim (IRR = 1.040, $p < 0.019$), the prevalence of questionable research practices increases by almost 10% and 4% respectively. For each unit increase on the relateability-scale of condemning condemners (IRR = 1.05, $p < 0.013$) and appealing to higher loyalties (IRR = 1.055, $p < 0.004$), the threshold of questionable research practices increases by 5% and 5,5%.

For each model, we also computed a logistic regression to check for robustness, for which the results point in the same direction. Following analysis of the full model we also examine interactions between the key and control variables. None of the interactions of neutralisation

and gender and neutralisation and status were substantial. The results are available upon request.

Table 1. Estimated results of the Poisson regressions of the effect of the neutralization techniques on the misconduct counts (Model 1), on the questionable research counts (Model 2) and on the severe scientific misconduct counts (Model 3) are shown as incidence rate ratios; * $p < 0.05$; ** $p < 0.01$. Robust standard errors are in parentheses.

	DV: Misconduct scale	DV: QRP scale	DV: SSM scale
Variables	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3
Denial of responsibility	1.106** (0.20)	1.099** (0.02)	SSM scale
Denial of injury	1.021 (0.02)	0.983 (0.02)	1.164** (0.06)
Denial of victim	1.038* (0.02)	1.040* (0.02)	1.209** (0.72)
Condemnation of Condemners	1.067** (0.02)	1.052* (0.02)	1.023 (0.06)
Appeal to higher loyalties	1.054** (0.02)	1.055** (0.02)	1.157* (0.07)
<i>Gender (ref. male)</i>			
Female	0.915 (0.04)	0.909* (0.04)	1.051 (0.06)
<i>Status (ref. predoc)</i>			
Postdoc	1.485** (0.09)	1.612** (0.08)	0.965 (0.15)
Prof	1.906** (0.12)	2.073** (0.12)	0.862 (0.16)
<i>Field (ref. hum. & social sci.)</i>			
Life Sciences	1.023 (0.07)	1.055 (0.06)	0.782 (0.19)
Natural Sciences	1.045 (0.07)	1.08 (0.06)	0.795 (0.19)
Engineering	1.123 (0.08)	1.157* (0.07)	0.932 (0.21)
<i>Country (ref. Germany)</i>			
Austria	1.039 (0.06)	1.021 (0.06)	1.204 (0.23)
Switzerland	0.797** (0.05)	0.784** (0.04)	0.914 (0.19)
N	3,177	3,177	3,177
Mc Fadden's R2	0.044	0.041	0.040
AIC	2.211	2.2019	0.571

The current study thus makes three major contributions to existing literature. First, we can provide an up-to-date understanding of how prevalent scientific misconduct is in the academic systems of Germany, Austria and Switzerland. Second, this study is the first to look at the relationship between neutralisation and scientific misconduct among researchers. This approach does therefore advance the criminological literature on neutralisation, as we apply this in a new context. Third, through the implementation of the techniques we provide an enhanced understanding of scientific misconduct – what the context is in which it takes place. In doing so, we offer individuals and institutions the opportunity to target risky discourses to prevent the emergence of an academic culture that triggers scientific misconduct. Ideally, we would like to provide the tools to neutralise the neutralisation of misbehaviour and in doing so help find ways to prevent misconduct.

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